

Consumers' preference for reduced pesticide use in conventional vineyards: A reference price-dependent discrete choice experimental approach

Noah Larvoe^{*a}, Zein Kallas^{a, b}, and Felicidad De Herralde^b

^aCentre for Agro-food Economy & Development-Universitat Polytechnic de Catalunya, CREDA-UPC, Castelldefels, noah.larvoe@upc.edu

^bInstituto de Investigación y Tecnologías Agroalimentarias, IRTA, España

Introduction

- As a result of the rising concerns of **PESTICIDE USE**, the European Commission (EC) is taking urgent steps to **REDUCE** agriculture's dependency on pesticides.
- The EC is targeting a **50% REDUCTION** in pesticide use **BY 2030** through the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity strategies under the **GREEN DEAL** (Montanarella & Panagos, 2021; Tataridas et al., 2022).
- Successful achievement of the **EC'S PESTICIDE TARGET** depends **NOT** only on **FARMERS** **BUT** also **CONSUMERS' WTP** for sustainable products.
- The study uses the **MEDITERRANEAN VINEYARD SECTOR** as a case study to investigate consumer's **WTP** for **CONVENTIONAL WINES** produced from reduced pesticide use.

Objective

- To determine the **PREMIUM** that wine consumers place on conventional wines produced from reduced pesticide use in vineyards.

Methods

- DYNAMIC CONSUMER-REFERENCE PRICE** based **discrete choice experiment**:

- SOLEMN OATH** and **CHEAP-TALK** scripts used to control **HYPOTHETICAL BIAS** (Carlson et al., 2005; De-Magistris and Pascucci, 2014)
- 5.091 CONSUMERS** in France, Greece, Italy, Portugal and Spain.

Table 1: Attributes, definition and levels

Attribute	Definition	Base	Lev.1	Lev.2	Lev.3
PESTICIDE REDUCTION	Percentage pesticide reduction in vineyards	-10%	-20%	-30%	-40%
CERTIFICATION	Use of labels/stamps to signify compliance with pesticide reduction	NC	IC	PC	EC
PRICE	Market price based on consumers' previous price in Euros (€) for a 750ml standard wine bottle	50%	5%	20%	35%

NC=No certification, IC=Independent certification, PC=Participatory guaranteed certification, EC=EU/National government certification

Example of choice card: You indicated that you usually pay **2.55 €** for your **750ML BOTTLE** of **RED** wine for regular consumption at home. Which red wine below will you purchase for your usual home consumption based on the level of **PESTICIDE REDUCED**, **PRICE**, and **CERTIFICATION? IMAGINE** that these **RED** wines are from the same **BRAND** and have the **SAME ATTRIBUTES** and **CHARACTERISTICS** as those you usually purchase (usual occasion) for regular home consumption.

The preference for consumers is estimated using **THE RANDOM PARAMETER LOGIT (RPL)** model that allows for heterogeneity. The utility of the *i*-th consumer when he selects a bottle of wine *j* in the choice task *s* can be written as:

$$U_{ijs} = \alpha PRC_{ijs} + \beta_i X_{ijs} + ASC + \varepsilon_{ijs}$$

where

ASC = alternative-specific constant for no buy option(status quo).

PRC = price levels

β_i = vector of the utility parameters

X_{ij} = vector of other wine attributes,

ε_{ijs} = an unobserved random term.

The willingness to pay for a utility bearing attribute is estimated as: $WTP = \beta_n / \alpha_i$

Results

Table 2: socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Country	France	Greece	Italy	Portugal	Spain
Sample	1013	1018	1021	1021	1018
Gender					
Female	51.0%	51.1%	50.2%	51.7%	50.4%
Male	48.9%	48.6%	49.1%	48.1%	49.4%
Age categories					
18-24 years	11.7%	9.2%	9.5%	9.7%	9.2%
25-34 years	16.2%	15.8%	15.1%	15.6%	15.9%
35-44 years	18.5%	20.3%	19.1%	20.8%	21.9%
45-54 years	19.5%	21.2%	22.6%	20.7%	21.9%
>55 years	34.1%	33.4%	33.7%	33.3%	31.0%
< 1.000 €	9.3%	41.6%	16.7%	42.6%	17.9%
1.000-2.000 €	34.9%	39.1%	47.5%	40.5%	44.3%
2.001-3.000 €	26.9%	10.0%	20.3%	11.7%	23.7%
3.001-4.000 €	13.7%	2.8%	5.7%	2.3%	6.5%
4.001-5.000 €	7.0%	2.1%	4.5%	1.1%	3.6%
> 5.000 €	8.1%	4.5%	5.3%	1.9%	4.0%
Net monthly household income					

- Balanced data with representation drawn from different categories of gender, age and income groups.

Discussion

Results from the RPL in **Table 3** model shows:

- NEGATIVE** and **SIGNIFICANT PRICE PARAMETERS** across all five countries with highest **PRICE SENSITIVITY** in France(-0.039) and lowest in Italy(-0.023).
- NEGATIVE ASC PARAMETERS** for all countries implying **LESS PREFERENCE** for conventional wines with no effort to reduce pesticides(status quo).
- ALL CERTIFICATION** types except **IC** are **POSITIVE** and highly significant preference for **CERTIFIED WINES**.

Table 3: Results of the random parameter logit model

	France	Greece	Italy	Portugal	Spain
Pesticide reduction	0.023*** (0.006)	0.053*** (0.005)	0.045*** (.006)	0.044*** (0.005)	0.024*** (0.006)
IC	0.176*** (0.038)	-0.036 (0.038)	0.002 (0.038)	0.143*** (0.035)	-0.064* (0.035)
PC	0.093** (0.044)	0.243*** (0.044)	0.127*** (0.045)	0.043*** (0.040)	0.079** (0.041)
EC	0.285*** (0.043)	1.216*** (0.062)	0.757*** (0.054)	0.873*** (0.052)	0.880*** (0.051)
PRICE	-0.039*** (0.002)	-0.033*** (0.002)	-0.023*** (0.002)	-0.033*** (0.002)	-0.034*** (0.002)
ASC	-1.353*** (0.076)	-1.330*** (0.076)	-1.091*** (0.079)	-1.439*** (0.072)	-1.235*** (0.072)
N	17,184	18,360	17,208	22,416	19,872
McFadden R-squared	0.235	0.275	0.2708	0.276	0.252

***, **, * ==> Significance at 1%, 5%, 10% level and Standard error in parentheses

- The **WTP** estimates in **Table 4** shows that respondents are willing to pay from **24% UP TO 84% more of their previous average price** for red wines produced from vineyards with 40% reduced pesticide use **DEPENDING** on the **COUNTRY** and the **CERTIFICATION TYPE**.

Table 4: Willingness to pay for wine from reduced pesticide use

Country	WTP (40% pesticide reduction without certification)	WTP (40% pesticide reduction with certification)
France	23.67	30.93
Greece	63.86	71.14
Italy	78.80	84.29
Portugal	53.56	80.35
Spain	27.92	53.80

Conclusion

The outcome of the study proves that a **POTENTIAL MARKET** exists for wine producers who are willing to reduce pesticide use in their vineyards. Thus, if **LABELS** can be used to differentiate conventional wines in terms of the levels of pesticide used in the vineyards, those with higher pesticide reductions are likely to receive **HIGHER PREMIUM PRICE** for their products.